

On Neutrosophic Crisp Semi Alpha Closed Sets

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Abstract. In this paper, we presented another concept of neutrosophic crisp generalized closed sets called neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets and studied their fundamental properties in neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. We also present neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closure and neutrosophic crisp semi- α -interior and study some of their fundamental properties.

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1. Introduction

The concept of "neutrosophic set" was first given by F. Smarandache [4,5]. A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblawi [1] presented the concept of neutrosophic topological space (briefly NTS). Q. H. Imran, F. Smarandache, R. K. Al-Hamido and R. Dhavaseelan [6] presented the idea of neutrosophic semi- α -open sets in neutrosophic topological spaces. In 2014, A. A. Salama, F. Smarandache and V. Kroumov [2] presented the concept of neutrosophic crisp topological space (briefly NCTS). The objective of this paper is to present the concept of neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets and study their fundamental properties in neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. We also present neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closure and neutrosophic crisp semi- α -interior and obtain some of its properties.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, (\mathcal{U}, T) (or simply \mathcal{U}) always mean a neutrosophic crisp topological space. The complement of a neutrosophic crisp open set (briefly NC-OS) is called a neutrosophic crisp closed set (briefly NC-CS) in (\mathcal{U}, T) . For a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , $NCcl(\mathcal{A})$, $NCint(\mathcal{A})$ and \mathcal{A}^c denote the neutrosophic crisp closure of \mathcal{A} , the neutrosophic crisp interior of \mathcal{A} and the neutrosophic crisp complement of \mathcal{A} , respectively.

Definition 2.1:

A neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is said to be:

(i) A neutrosophic crisp pre-open set (briefly NCP-OS) [3] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A}))$. The complement of a NCP-OS is called a neutrosophic crisp pre-closed set (briefly NCP-CS) in (\mathcal{U}, T) . The family of all NCP-OS (resp. NCP-CS) of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $NCPO(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $NCPC(\mathcal{U})$).

(ii) A neutrosophic crisp semi-open set (briefly NCS-OS) [3] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$. The complement of a NCS-OS is called a neutrosophic crisp semi-closed set (briefly NCS-CS) in (\mathcal{U}, T) . The family of all NCS-OS (resp. NCS-CS) of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $NCSO(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $NCSC(\mathcal{U})$).

(iii) A neutrosophic crisp α -open set (briefly $NC\alpha$ -OS) [3] if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$. The complement of a $NC\alpha$ -OS is called a neutrosophic crisp α -closed set (briefly $NC\alpha$ -CS) in (\mathcal{U}, T) . The family of all $NC\alpha$ -OS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -CS) of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $NC\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$ (resp. $NC\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$).

Definition 2.2:

(i) The neutrosophic crisp pre-interior of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the union of all NCP-OS contained in \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $PNCint(\mathcal{A})$ [3].

- (ii) The neutrosophic crisp semi-interior of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the union of all NCS-OS contained in \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $SNCint(\mathcal{A})$ [3].
- (iii) The neutrosophic crisp α -interior of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the union of all $NC\alpha$ -OS contained in \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$ [3].

Definition 2.3:

- (i) The neutrosophic crisp pre-closure of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the intersection of all NCP-CS that contain \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $PNCcl(\mathcal{A})$ [3].
- (ii) The neutrosophic crisp semi-closure of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the intersection of all NCS-CS that contain \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $SNCcl(\mathcal{A})$ [3].
- (iii) The neutrosophic crisp α -closure of a neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is the intersection of all $NC\alpha$ -CS that contain \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ [3].

Proposition 2.4 [7]:

In a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following statements hold, and the equality of each statement are not true:

- (i) Every NC-CS (resp. NC-OS) is a $NC\alpha$ -CS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OS).
- (ii) Every $NC\alpha$ -CS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OS) is a NCS-CS (resp. NCS-OS).
- (iii) Every $NC\alpha$ -CS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OS) is a NCP-CS (resp. NCP-OS).

Proposition 2.5 [7]:

A neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is a $NC\alpha$ -CS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OS) iff \mathcal{A} is a NCS-CS (resp. NCS-OS) and NCP-CS (resp. NCP-OS).

Theorem 2.6 [7]:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , $\mathcal{A} \in NC\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$ iff there exists a NC-OS \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$.

Proposition 2.7 [7]:

The union of any family of $NC\alpha$ -OS is a $NC\alpha$ -OS.

Proposition 2.8:

- (i) If \mathcal{K} is a NC-OS, then $SNCcl(\mathcal{K}) = NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{K}))$.
- (ii) If \mathcal{A} is a neutrosophic crisp subset of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , then $SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})))$.

Proof: This follows directly from the definition (2.1) and proposition (2.4).

3. Neutrosophic Crisp Semi- α -Closed Sets

In this section, we present and study the neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets and some of its properties.

Definition 3.1:

A neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is called neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed set (briefly NCS α -CS) if there exists a $NC\alpha$ -CS \mathcal{H} in \mathcal{U} such that $NCint(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ or equivalently if $NCint(\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. The family of all NCS α -CS of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.

Definition 3.2:

A neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{A} is called a neutrosophic crisp semi- α -open set (briefly NCS α -OS) if and only if its complement \mathcal{A}^c is a NCS α -CS or equivalently if there exists a $NC\alpha$ -OS \mathcal{H} in \mathcal{U} such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{H})$. The family of all NCS α -OS of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.

Proposition 3.3:

It is evident by definitions that in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following hold:

- (i) Every NC-CS (resp. NC-OS) is a NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS).
- (ii) Every $NC\alpha$ -CS (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OS) is a NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS).

The converse of Proposition (3.3) need not be true as shown by the following example.

Example 3.4:

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{p, q, r, s\}$, $\mathcal{A} = \{\{p\}, \{q, s\}, \{r\}\}$, $\mathcal{B} = \{\{p\}, \{q\}, \{r\}\}$. Then $T = \{\emptyset_N, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}_N\}$ is a neutrosophic crisp topology on \mathcal{U} .

- (i) Let $\mathcal{H} = \langle \{p\}, \{q, r, s\}, \emptyset \rangle$, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{H} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_N$, the neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{H} is a NCS α -OS but not NC-OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{H}^c = \langle \{q, r, s\}, \{p\}, \mathcal{U} \rangle$ is a NCS α -CS but not NC-CS.
- (ii) Let $\mathcal{K} = \langle \emptyset, \{q, r, s\}, \{r, s\} \rangle$ and so $\mathcal{K} \notin NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{K})))$, the neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{K} is a NCS α -OS but not NC α -OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{K}^c = \langle \mathcal{U}, \{p\}, \{p, q\} \rangle$ is a NCS α -CS but not NC α -CS.

Remark 3.5:

The concepts of NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS) and NCP-CS (resp. NCP-OS) are independent, as the following examples show.

Example 3.6:

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{p, q, r, s\}$, $\mathcal{A} = \langle \{p\}, \{q\}, \{r\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{B} = \langle \{r\}, \{q\}, \{s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{C} = \langle \{p, r\}, \{q\}, \emptyset \rangle$, $\mathcal{D} = \langle \emptyset, \{q\}, \{r, s\} \rangle$. Then $T = \{\emptyset_N, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{U}_N\}$ is a neutrosophic crisp topology on \mathcal{U} . Let $\mathcal{H} = \langle \{r, s\}, \{p, q\}, \{s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{H} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{B}) = \langle \{r, s\}, \{q\}, \emptyset \rangle$, the neutrosophic crisp set \mathcal{H} is a NCS α -OS but not NCP-OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{H}^c = \langle \{s\}, \{p, q\}, \{r, s\} \rangle$ is a NCS α -CS but not NCP-CS.

Example 3.7:

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{p, q, r, s\}$, $\mathcal{A}_1 = \langle \{p\}, \{q\}, \{r\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{A}_2 = \langle \{p\}, \{q, s\}, \{r\} \rangle$. Then $T = \{\emptyset_N, \mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{U}_N\}$ is a neutrosophic crisp topology on \mathcal{U} . If $\mathcal{A}_3 = \langle \{p, q\}, \{r\}, \{s\} \rangle$, then \mathcal{A}_3 is a NCP-OS but not NCS α -OS. It is clear that $\mathcal{A}_3^c = \langle \{s\}, \{r\}, \{p, q\} \rangle$ is a NCP-CS but not NCS α -CS.

Remark 3.8:

- (i) If every NC-OS is a NC-CS and every nowhere neutrosophic crisp dense set is NC-CS in any neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , then every NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS) is a NC-CS (resp. NC-OS).
- (ii) If every NC-OS is a NC-CS in any neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , then every NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS) is a NC α -CS (resp. NC α -OS).

Remark 3.9:

- (i) It is clear that every NCS-CS (resp. NCS-OS) and NCP-CS (resp. NCP-OS) of any neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is a NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS) (by Proposition (2.5) and Proposition (3.3) (ii)).
- (ii) A NCS α -CS (resp. NCS α -OS) in any neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) is a NCP-CS (resp. NCP-OS) if every NC-OS of \mathcal{U} is a NC-CS (from Proposition (2.4) (iii) and Remark (3.8) (ii)).

Theorem 3.10:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) . The following properties are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.
- (ii) There exists a NC-OS, say \mathcal{H} , such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$. Then, there exists $\mathcal{K} \in NC\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$, such that $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{K})$. Hence there exists \mathcal{H} NC-OS such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$ (by Theorem (2.6)). Therefore, $NCcl(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$, implies that $NCcl(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$. Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{K}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$. Hence, $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$, for some \mathcal{H} NC-OS.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Suppose that there exists a NC-OS \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$. We know that $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. On the other hand, $\mathcal{H} \subseteq NCint(\mathcal{A})$ (since $NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest NC-OS contained in \mathcal{A}). Hence $NCcl(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$, then $NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})) \subseteq NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$, therefore $NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$. But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$ (by hypothesis). Hence $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$. To prove $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$, let $\mathcal{K} = NCint(\mathcal{A})$; we know that $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. To prove $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Since $NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Hence, $NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq NCcl(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))) = NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$.

But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ (by hypothesis). Hence, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$

$\subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$. Hence, there exists an NC-OS say \mathcal{K} , such that $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{A})$. On the other hand, \mathcal{K} is a NC α -OS (since \mathcal{K} is a NC-OS). Hence $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 3.11:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$.
- (ii) There exists a NC-CS \mathcal{F} such that $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.
- (iii) $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$, then $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Hence there is \mathcal{H} NC-OS such that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A}^c \subseteq \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{H})))$ (by Theorem (3.10)). Hence $(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{H}))))^c \subseteq \mathcal{A}^c \subseteq \mathcal{H}^c$, i.e., $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{H}^c))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{H}^c$. Let $\mathcal{H}^c = \mathcal{F}$, where \mathcal{F} is a NC-CS in \mathcal{U} .

Then $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Suppose that there exists \mathcal{F} NC-CS such that $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, but $\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest NC-CS containing \mathcal{A} . Then $\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, and therefore: $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \text{NCint}(\mathcal{F})$

$\Rightarrow \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{F})) \Rightarrow \text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. To prove $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$, i.e., to prove $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Then $\mathcal{A}^c \subseteq (\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A}))))^c = \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$, but $(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\mathcal{A}))))^c = \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$.

Hence $\mathcal{A}^c \subseteq \text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\text{NCcl}(\text{NCint}(\mathcal{A}^c))))$, and therefore $\mathcal{A}^c \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$, i.e., $\mathcal{A} \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{U})$.

Theorem 3.12:

The union of any family of $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}$.

Proof: Let $\{\mathcal{A}_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a family of $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}$. To prove $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_\lambda$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}$. Since $\mathcal{A}_\lambda \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$. Then there is a NC-OS \mathcal{B}_λ such that $\mathcal{B}_\lambda \subseteq \mathcal{A}_\lambda \subseteq \text{NCcl}(\mathcal{B}_\lambda)$, $\forall \lambda \in \Lambda$. Hence $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_\lambda \subseteq \bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_\lambda \subseteq \bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \text{NCcl}(\mathcal{B}_\lambda) \subseteq \text{NCcl}(\bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_\lambda)$. But $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{B}_\lambda \in \text{NC}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$ (by Proposition (2.7)). Hence $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_\lambda \in \text{NCS}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 3.13:

The intersection of any family of $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$.

Proof: This follows directly from Theorem (3.12).

Remark 3.14:

The following diagram shows the relations among the different types of weakly neutrosophic crisp closed sets that were studied in this section:

Diagram (3.1)

4. Neutrosophic Crisp Semi- α -Closure and Neutrosophic Crisp Semi- α -Interior

We present neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closure and neutrosophic crisp semi- α -interior and obtain some of their properties in this section.

Definition 4.1:

The intersection of all NCS α -CS in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) containing \mathcal{A} is called neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closure of \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$, $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = \bigcap \{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}\}$.

Definition 4.2:

The union of all NCS α -OS in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) contained in \mathcal{A} is called neutrosophic crisp semi- α -interior of \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$, $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) = \bigcup \{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}\}$.

Proposition 4.3:

Let \mathcal{A} be any neutrosophic crisp set in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following properties are true:

- (i) $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$ iff \mathcal{A} is a NCS α -CS.
- (ii) $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$ iff \mathcal{A} is a NCS α -OS.
- (iii) $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest NCS α -CS containing \mathcal{A} .
- (iv) $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest NCS α -OS contained in \mathcal{A} .

Proof: (i), (ii), (iii) and (iv) are obvious.

Proposition 4.4:

Let \mathcal{A} be any neutrosophic crisp set in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following properties hold:

- (i) $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{U}_N - \mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_N - (S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}))$,
- (ii) $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{U}_N - \mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_N - (S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Proof: (i) By definition (2.3), $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = \bigcap \{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_N - (S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) &= \mathcal{U}_N - \bigcap \{\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}\} \\ &= \bigcup \{\mathcal{U}_N - \mathcal{B} : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}\} \\ &= \bigcup \{\mathcal{H} : \mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{U}_N - \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{H} \text{ is a NCS}\alpha\text{-OS}\} \\ &= S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{U}_N - \mathcal{A}). \end{aligned}$$

- (ii) The proof is similar to (i).

Theorem 4.5:

Let \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} be two neutrosophic crisp sets in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) . The following properties hold:

- (i) $S\alpha NCcl(\emptyset_N) = \emptyset_N$, $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{U}_N) = \mathcal{U}_N$.
- (ii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.
- (iv) $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \cap S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.
- (v) $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \cup S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.
- (vi) $S\alpha NCcl(S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: (i) and (ii) are evident.

(iii) By (ii), $\mathcal{B} \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$. Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, we have $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$. But $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$ is a NCS α -CS. Thus $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$ is a NCS α -CS containing \mathcal{A} .

Since $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ is the smallest NCS α -CS containing \mathcal{A} , we have $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$. Hence, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.

(iv) We know that $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Therefore, by (iii), $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ and $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$. Hence $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \cap S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.

(v) Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$, it follows from part (iii) that $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$ and $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$. Hence $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \cup S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.

(vi) Since $S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ is a NCS α -CS, we have by Proposition (4.3)(i), $S\alpha NCcl(S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.

Theorem 4.6:

Let \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} be two neutrosophic crisp sets in a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) . The following properties hold:

- (i) $S\alpha NCint(\emptyset_N) = \emptyset_N$, $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{U}_N) = \mathcal{U}_N$.
- (ii) $S\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

- (iii) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{B})$.
- (iv) $SaNCint(\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \cap SaNCint(\mathcal{B})$.
- (v) $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \cup SaNCint(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$.
- (vi) $SaNCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: (i), (ii), (iii), (iv), (v) and (vi) are obvious.

Proposition 4.7:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , then:

- (i) $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (ii) $NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(NCint(\mathcal{A})) = NCint(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iii) $\alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$.
- (iv) $NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (v) $\alpha NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCcl(\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.
- (vi) $SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cup NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A}))))$.
- (vii) $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$.
- (viii) $NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq SaNCint(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Proof: We shall prove only (ii), (iii), (iv), (vii) and (viii).

(ii) To prove $NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(NCint(\mathcal{A})) = NCint(\mathcal{A})$, we know that $NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is a NC-OS. It follows that $NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is a NCS α -OS. Hence $NCint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNCint(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$ (by Proposition (4.3)).

Therefore: $NCint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNCint(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$(1)

Since $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow NCint(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A}))$. Also, $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence: $NCint(\mathcal{A}) = NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A}))$(2)

Therefore by (1) and (2), we get $NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(NCint(\mathcal{A})) = NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

(iii) Now we prove $\alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

Since $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is NC α -OS, therefore $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$ is NCS α -OS. Therefore by Proposition (4.3):

$\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) = SaNCint(\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}))$(1)

Now, to prove $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) = \alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A}))$, we have $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow \alpha NCint(\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A}))$.

Also, $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence: $\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A}) = \alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A}))$(2)

Therefore by (1) and (2), we get $\alpha NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCint(\alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})) = \alpha NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

(iv) To prove $NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = NCcl(\mathcal{A})$. We know that $NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ is a NC-CS, so it is NCS α -CS. Hence by proposition (4.3), we have: $NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = SaNCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A}))$(1)

To prove $NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$, we have $SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{A})$ (by part (i)).

Then $NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.

Since $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$.

Hence, $NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))) = NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow NCcl(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$

and therefore: $NCcl(\mathcal{A}) = NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$(2)

Now, by (1) and (2), we get that $NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A}))$. Hence $NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})) = SaNCcl(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) = NCcl(\mathcal{A})$.

(vii) To prove $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$, since $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U}) \Rightarrow SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(SaNCint(\mathcal{A})))) = NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$

(by part (ii)). Hence, $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$, also $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then:

$SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$(1)

To prove $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ is a NCS α -OS contained in \mathcal{A} .

It is clear that $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ and also it is clear that $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow NCint(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))) \Rightarrow NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))) \Rightarrow NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$ and $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ and $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$. We get $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$. Hence $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ is a NCS α -OS (by Proposition (4.3)). Also, $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ is contained in \mathcal{A} .

Then $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A})$ (since $SaNCint(\mathcal{A})$ is the largest NCS α - OS contained in \mathcal{A}). Hence: $\mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNCint(\mathcal{A})$(2)

By (1) and (2), we get that $SaNCint(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A} \cap NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$.

(viii) To prove that $NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq SaNCint(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A}))$, we know that $SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})$ is a NCS α -CS, therefore $NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})$ (by Corollary (3.11)). Hence $NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})))) \subseteq SaNCcl(\mathcal{A})$ (by part (iv)). Therefore,

$S\alpha NCint(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A}))) \subseteq S\alpha NCint(S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \Rightarrow NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{A})) \subseteq S\alpha NCint(S\alpha NCcl(\mathcal{A}))$ (by (ii)).

Theorem 4.8:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{A} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) . The following properties are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.
- (ii) $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$, for some NC-OS \mathcal{H} .
- (iii) $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some NC-OS \mathcal{H} .
- (iv) $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $\mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$, then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ and $NCint(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Hence $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$, where $\mathcal{H} = NCint(\mathcal{A})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Suppose $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$, for some NC-OS \mathcal{H} . But $SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})) = NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})))$ (by Proposition (2.8)). Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some NC-OS \mathcal{H} .

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv) Suppose that $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$, for some NC-OS \mathcal{H} . Since \mathcal{H} is a NC-OS contained in \mathcal{A} . Then $\mathcal{H} \subseteq NCint(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow NCcl(\mathcal{H}) \subseteq NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))$

$\Rightarrow SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H})) \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$. But $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(\mathcal{H}))$ (by hypothesis), then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i) Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq SNCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))$.

But $SNCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))) = NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A}))))$ (by Proposition (2.8)).

Hence, $\mathcal{A} \subseteq NCcl(NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{A})))) \Rightarrow \mathcal{A} \in NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{U})$.

Corollary 4.9:

For any neutrosophic crisp subset \mathcal{B} of a neutrosophic crisp topological space (\mathcal{U}, T) , the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathcal{B} \in NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.
- (ii) $NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS.
- (iii) $SNCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS.
- (iv) $SNCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $\mathcal{B} \in NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{U}) \Rightarrow NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ (by Corollary(3.11)) and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{B})$. Hence we obtain $NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.

Therefore, $NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, where $\mathcal{F} = NCcl(\mathcal{B})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Let $NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS. But $NCint(NCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F}))) = SNCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F}))$ (by Proposition (2.8)). Hence $SNCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv) Let $SNCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, for some \mathcal{F} NC-CS. Since $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ (by hypothesis), then we have $NCcl(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{F} \Rightarrow NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B})) \subseteq NCint(\mathcal{F}) \Rightarrow SNCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq SNCcl(NCint(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow SNCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i) Let $SNCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$.

But $SNCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))) = NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B}))))$ (by Proposition (2.8)).

Hence, $NCint(NCcl(NCint(NCcl(\mathcal{B})))) \subseteq \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \mathcal{B} \in NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{U})$.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we have the new concept of neutrosophic crisp closed sets called neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets and studied their fundamental properties in neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. The neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets can obtain to derive a new decomposition of neutrosophic crisp continuity.

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